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The Effect of Different Command Method Exercises on Reaction Time in Adolescent Soccer Players

Adölesan Futbolcularda Farklı Komut Yöntemi Antrenmanlarının Reaksiyon Zamanına Etkisi

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effects of visual, auditory, and tactile command-based exercises on reaction time in adolescent soccer players. Thirty-two male players aged 10–15 years participated to determine which command method was most effective over a short period. The study was designed according to a controlled pre-posttest experimental design from quantitative research methods. The participants in the study were divided into four groups: Visual, Auditory, Tactile, and Control (VG, AG, TG, CG) using a complete randomization method. Performed command trainings 2 days a week for a total of 8 weeks. One day before the 8-week training program, the visual reaction times of the soccer players were tested for pre-test data. After completing the 8-week training period, visual reaction times were tested again one day after the last training week for post-test data. The visual reaction tests of the football players were measured in 5 repetitions with appropriate application programs and averaged. After conducting the normality test on the obtained data, a Paired Sample t-test was used to compare the pre- and post-test reaction times. One-way ANOVA was used for comparing the mean differences in reaction times between the groups from the pre-post test, and the LSD test was used for multiple group comparisons. As a result of the statistical analysis of the data obtained, a significant difference was found in favor of the post-test in visual reaction times in all groups except the control group ($p < 0.05$). In the comparison of mean differences between groups, significant differences were found in the visual, auditory, and tactile command training groups and the control group ($p < 0.05$). As a result of the study, exercises with different command methods have positive effects on visual reaction time in adolescent soccer players.

Keywords: Sportive Performance, Reaction Time, Soccer.

ÖZET

Bu çalışma, görsel, işitsel ve dokunsal olmak üzere farklı komut yöntemleriyle yapılan egzersizlerin ergen futbolcuların tepki süresi üzerindeki etkisini araştırmayı amaçlamıştır. Bu amaçla, 10-15 yaşları arasındaki 32 erkek ergen futbolcu çalışmaya dahil edilerek, farklı komut yöntemlerinden hangisinin kısa sürede daha etkili olduğu belirlenmiştir. Çalışma, nicel araştırma yöntemlerinden kontrollü ön test-son test deneysel tasarıma göre tasarlanmıştır. Çalışmaya katılanlar, tam rastgele bir yöntem kullanılarak dört gruba ayrılmıştır: Görsel, İşitsel, Dokunsal ve Kontrol (VG, AG, TG, CG). Komut antrenmanları haftada 2 gün, toplam 8 hafta boyunca gerçekleştirilmiştir. 8 haftalık antrenman programından bir gün önce, futbolcuların görsel tepki süreleri ön test verileri için test edilmiştir. 8 haftalık eğitim dönemini tamamladıktan sonra, son eğitim haftasından bir gün sonra görsel tepki süreleri test sonrası verileri için tekrar test edildi. Futbolcuların görsel tepki süreleri, uygun uygulama programları ile 5 tekrar halinde ölçüldü ve ortalaması alındı. Elde edilen veriler üzerinde normallik testi yapıldıktan sonra, test öncesi ve sonrası tepki sürelerini karşılaştırmak için Eşleştirilmiş Örnek t-testi kullanıldı. Ön-son test grupları arasındaki reaksiyon sürelerinin ortalama farklarını karşılaştırmak için tek yönlü ANOVA, çoklu grup karşılaştırmaları için ise LSD testi kullanılmıştır. Elde edilen verilerin istatistiksel analizi sonucunda, kontrol grubu hariç tüm gruplarda görsel reaksiyon sürelerinde son test lehine anlamlı bir fark bulunmuştur ($p < 0,05$). Gruplar arasındaki ortalama farkların karşılaştırılmasında, görsel, işitsel ve dokunsal komut eğitimi grupları ile kontrol grubu arasında anlamlı farklar bulunmuştur ($p < 0,05$). Çalışma sonucunda, farklı komut yöntemleri ile yapılan egzersizlerin ergen futbolcuların görsel tepki süresi üzerinde olumlu etkileri olduğu görülmüştür.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Sportif Performans, Reaksiyon Zamanı, Futbol.

1. INTRODUCTION

Reaction time is the interval between the presentation of a stimulus and the response to it. For instance, an athlete's response to the sound of a gunshot at the start of a race is considered a stimulus, and the time between hearing the sound and the athlete's response is defined as reaction time (Ertavukcu et al., 2021; Baayen & Milin, 2010). Reaction time is generally categorized into two types: simple and complex. In simple reaction time, there is only one stimulus. In contrast, in complex reaction time tasks, there are multiple stimuli and various response options to these stimuli. Therefore, simple reaction time is generally shorter than complex reaction time (Baayen & Milin, 2010). At the same time, reaction plays a crucial role in most sports, enabling individuals to make a difference in both individual and team sports, especially football (Demiryol, 2024). In soccer, an athlete's ability to respond appropriately to stimuli and make optimal decisions is critical to performance. Therefore, developing soccer players' reaction skills directly affects their performance (Zouhal et al., 2018). In addition to motor skills, cognitive ability is one of the factors that determine reaction time. Reaction time is influenced by factors such as reflex level, agility, and individual characteristics (Badau, Baydil, & Badau, 2018). Evaluating an athlete's performance in soccer requires measuring responses to auditory and visual stimuli. Soccer's large field and team dynamic, which require quick decision-making, increase the importance of reaction time in this sport (Thakur & Babu, 2016).

Research in the literature has examined the effect of reaction training on performance criteria in athletes from different sports (Vurmaz, 2016) and the relationship between reaction times and performance (Karadağ & Kutlu, 2006; Çakıroğlu & Sökmen, 2012; Çelikel, Sezer, and Karadağ, 2020; Pular & Akcan, 2017). Additionally, studies have compared the reaction times of active athletes across different sports and age groups, considering disciplines and positions (Hasçelik et al., 1989; Moka et al., 1992). However, few studies have compared the contributions of visual, auditory, and tactile reaction training within the same time frame. Furthermore, there is a lack of research examining the differences between athletes whose reaction time development is expected to occur through maturation associated with developmental stages and athletes whose reaction time is targeted for improvement through training during these stages.

This study aims to determine which method is more effective in improving reaction time over a specific period and to reveal the difference between athletes who perform visual, auditory, and tactile reaction exercises and those who do not engage in any reaction training. In this context, the primary objective of the study is to determine the most effective methods for improving reaction time in male soccer players at their developmental stage and to investigate the impact of various reaction training methods on reaction time over 8 weeks.

2. METHOD

2.1. Study Design and Participants

This study employed a controlled pretest–posttest experimental design. A total of 32 male soccer players aged 10–15 years, selected from among soccer school students who regularly attend soccer training, were included in the study. Participants were randomly assigned to four separate groups, each consisting of eight individuals, and each group was subjected to a different application protocol. Obtained from informed consent forms of the athletes participating in the study, and the Social and Human Sciences Ethics Committee of Gaziantep University provided the necessary ethical approval.

Table 1. Descriptive characteristics of the volunteers in the study

<i>Groups</i>		<i>Min.</i>	<i>Max.</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. D.</i>
<i>TG</i>	Years	12.00	15.00	12.88	0.99
	Body Weight (cm)	151.00	176.00	161.00	8.86
	Body Mass (kg)	35.00	60.00	47.13	9.49
<i>AG</i>	Years	10.00	14.00	11.63	1.41
	Body Weight (cm)	128.00	156.00	146.25	8.38
	Body Mass (kg)	27.00	55.00	39.13	8.90
<i>VG</i>	Years	12.00	13.00	12.63	0.52
	Body Weight (cm)	147.00	160.00	155.87	5.00
	Body Mass (kg)	35.00	65.00	47.63	10.11
<i>CG</i>	Years	10.00	14.00	12.38	1.60
	Body Weight (cm)	134.00	162.00	151.13	8.94
	Body Mass (kg)	25.00	65.00	43.75	13.20

VG: Visual Group; AG: Auditory Group; TG: Tactile Group; CG: Control Group; cm: centimeter; kg: kilogram

The study included four groups: the Visual Reaction Training Group (VG), the Auditory Reaction Training Group (AG), the Tactile Reaction Training Group (TG), and the Control Group (CG). An informational meeting was held with all participants prior to the application, explaining the purpose and content of the study. Pre-test measurements were then conducted by recording participants' visual reaction times and collecting their data.

The control group only participated in the pre- and post-test measurements, whereas the other three groups underwent pre- and post-test measurements in addition to the training protocols over 8 weeks. The intervention groups completed an 8-week training plan consisting of a total of 17 sessions (including pre- and post-tests). All sessions were conducted twice a week, prior to the athletes' regular weekly football training, using command-based training content.

Throughout the process, the details of each group's application were communicated to the coaches in detail and demonstrated in practice. All participants conducted their training sessions on the same days and at approximately the exact times. The command training sessions of the application groups are described below:

Visual Command Method Training

The visual reaction group (VG) started each training session for eight weeks with a soccer-specific warm-up without the ball, then stood in a static position behind the funnels waiting for the coach's visual stimulus (exit command). The athletes responded with a 10-meter sprint when they received the visual stimulus of the data. In each training session, performed in 20 repetitions, a whole rest period was given after each sprint.

Auditory Command Method Training

The auditory reaction group (AG) also started each session with a warm-up without a ball for eight weeks, and then waited for the coach's auditory command to go out with a whistle by taking a fixed position behind the funnels. The athletes responded to the whistle with a 10-meter sprint. In each training session, performed in 20 repetitions, a whole rest period was given after each sprint.

Tactile Command Method Training

The tactile reaction group (TG) began training with a warm-up exercise without the ball, similar to the other groups. Then, the athletes stood stationary behind the funnels and waited to receive the exit command, which was given by a teammate positioned behind them. The teammate standing behind provided the tactile stimulus by tapping at random timings, and the athlete responded with a 10-meter sprint. In each training session, performed in 20 repetitions, a whole rest period was given after each sprint.

2.2. Data Collection Tools

Prior to the administration of the measurements, the athletes were provided with a thorough explanation of the tests, their objectives, and the process. Provided this explanation to ensure that the athletes could focus their attention on the process. This implementation was undertaken as a strategy to enhance data reliability. Prior to the initial measurements, the athletes underwent a warm-up process similar to the one they had previously used before training. Prior to administering the reaction measurements, the program in which the test would be conducted was introduced, and each athlete was allowed to practice.

Visual Reaction Test

Utilized the program at <https://humanbenchmark.com/tests/reactiontime> to assess visual reaction times. In this experiment, subjects are instructed to wait for a blue screen to appear, and when the screen transitions to green, they are prompted to press the "space" key on the keyboard. The temporal discrepancy between the transition of the screen from blue to green and the athlete's actuation of the key is quantified and documented in milliseconds (ms). Obtained five measurements for each athlete in both the pre-test and post-test phases, and the mean of these measurements was utilized in the analysis (Bickmann et al., 2021).

2.3. Statistical Analysis

The data obtained from the study were analyzed using the SPSS 23.0 statistical program. The Shapiro-Wilk test was employed to evaluate the normality of the data distribution. The Paired Sample t-test was utilized to compare the pre- and post-test reaction times of the groups. To compare the mean differences in reaction times obtained from the pre- and post-tests between groups, a One-Way ANOVA and an LSD test were used. The findings were reported as mean, standard deviation, standard error, minimum, and maximum values, with a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

3. RESULTS

In this part of our study, statistical findings are presented to determine the effects of reaction training methods performed with different command methods on visual reaction times in soccer players.

Table 2. In-group comparison of visual reaction time averages of soccer players participating in the study

		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. D.</i>	<i>Std. E.</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
<i>VG</i>	Pre-test(ms)	443.23	50.06	17.70	4.554	0.003
	Post-test(ms)	360.60	26.29	9.29		
<i>AG</i>	Pre-test(ms)	413.83	50.00	17.68	5.622	0.001
	Post-test(ms)	380.60	57.18	20.22		
<i>TG</i>	Pre-test(ms)	393.35	25.42	8.99	4.785	0.002
	Post-test(ms)	348.55	30.64	10.83		
<i>CG</i>	Pre-test(ms)	359.65	45.26	16.00	0.609	0.562
	Post-test(ms)	354.23	34.70	12.27		

VG: Visual Group; AG: Auditory Group; TG: Tactile Group; CG: Control Group; ms: millisecond

Table 2 shows the comparison of pre- and post-test averages for visual reaction times among football players, based on an analysis of within-group changes. The statistical analysis revealed that reaction training based on different command methods aimed at improving visual reaction time produced significant differences in the average visual reaction times of all groups except the control group ($p < 0.05$). Examining the level of significance within the groups based on the change in average time revealed that the group that underwent reaction training using visual command methods showed the most improvement in visual reaction time. Conversely, no significant change was observed in the control group when comparing the pre- and post-test averages ($p > 0.05$).

Table 3. Comparison of visual reaction time pre-post test mean differences between groups

	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. D.</i>	<i>Std. E.</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Difference</i>
<i>VG</i>	82.62	51.31	18.14	7.713	0.001	G-I
<i>IG</i>	33.23	16.72	5.91			G-D
<i>AG</i>	44.80	26.48	9.36			G-K
<i>KG</i>	5.43	25.18	8.90			

VG: Visual Group; AG: Auditory Group; TG: Tactile Group; CG: Control Group; ms: millisecond

Table 3 shows the differences in visual reaction time measurements between the groups at both pre-test and post-test levels. Statistical analysis revealed a significant difference in mean pre- and post-test score differences between groups ($p < 0.05$). This difference favored the visual reaction training (VG) group, which showed greater improvement than the AG, TG, and CG groups.

Analysis of the Change in Visual Reaction Times of the Groups

VG: Visual Group; AG: Auditory Group; TG: Tactile Group; CG: Control Group; ms: millisecond

Figure 1. Analysis of the change in visual reaction times of the groups

4. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the impact of visual, auditory, and tactile command training on the development of visual reaction time, a crucial aspect in soccer. To this end, 32 male youth soccer players were randomly assigned to four groups (Visual Command Group [VG], Auditory Command Group [AG], Tactile Command Group [TG], and Control Group [CG]), each consisting of eight participants. The study consisted of an eight-week command training protocol. Took measurements one day before the

start of the application process as a pre-test and immediately after its completion as a post-test. Participants in the control group were only included in the pre- and post-test measurements and did not undergo any command training. The other three groups participated in command training sessions planned twice a week for eight weeks, according to their respective categories.

Upon evaluating the study's findings, it was observed that there were significant changes in the visual reaction times of child footballers compared to their pre-test values. As the training programme included visual, auditory, and tactile methods, one important result of the study is that these different types of stimuli also contributed significantly to visual reaction time. As in many sports, improved reaction time is critical for the practical application of sport-specific skills in football. The execution of goal-oriented moves is directly related to an athlete's ability to perceive stimuli quickly and generate the correct reaction (Schmidt, 1991; Pain et al., 2011). In this study, we analysed the duration of conscious responses formed by footballers to a visual stimulus to evaluate visual reaction times. The findings revealed a significant improvement in visual reaction time. Visual, auditory, and tactile command training all contributed significantly to the visual reaction times of football players.

A review of the literature reveals that previous studies have demonstrated the importance of reaction time in developing sport-specific skills (Çolakoğlu, Tiryaki & Molalı, 1993; Brito et al., 2022; Vanttinen et al., 2010). Research in this field emphasizes the importance of reaction training tailored to the needs of athletes in different sports (Stavropoulou & Stavropoulos, 2021). Studies have examined reaction times in football players (Alanazi & Aouadi, 2015; Flores et al., 2023), as well as investigated the impact of reaction training on fundamental motor skills in football (Eniseler, 2010; Aksoy & Agaoglu, 2017; Vanderford et al., 2004). A review of the current literature indicates that visual reaction time plays a critical role in football, particularly during matches and when applying sport-specific fundamental skills (Thakur & Babu, 2016).

Much of human reactive learning is achieved through visual means. Processing and interpreting visual stimuli perceived by the central nervous system, and forming an appropriate motor response, provides insight into reaction times (Kanadlı, 2010; Lucia et al., 2021). In football, the ability to respond quickly and effectively to visual stimuli, such as dribbling, shooting, tackling, and controlling the ball, during training and matches is crucial for achieving the desired level of performance (Çolakoğlu et al., 1993). Visual reaction time is a fundamental requirement for effectively demonstrating many sport-specific skills in football. This study also corroborates previous research, demonstrating a significant improvement in visual reaction time. However, the lack of significant change in the control group suggests that further work is needed to enhance reaction times in athletes who only engage in routine football training.

Previous studies have shown that various applications can be used to measure reaction time. For instance, Norrie (1967) found that, in his study, participants' reaction time decreased from 252 ms to 220 ms after the first ten trials. The variability of the obtained data can be attributed to several factors, including the measurement tool used, the characteristics of the sample, the warm-up conditions, the compatibility between the stimulus and the response, and the participants' age, gender, height, and training level (Sevim, 2010). Another study (Boyar, 2013) demonstrated that basic football training, conducted three days a week for 16 weeks, without additional reaction training, had a positive effect on the visual reaction times of children aged 9–14.

Another significant finding of our study emerged from analysing the mean differences in pre- and post-test scores between groups. When we compared the pre- and post-test differences between the groups, we found a significant difference in favour of the visual command training group. This reflects the visual nature of the tested reaction type, as well as the potential contribution of responses to visual stimuli in football to sport-specific success. As noted in the literature, visual reaction is the type of reaction most targeted for development in football and is crucial for the effective execution of goal-oriented skills (Çolakoğlu et al., 1993; Aksoy & Agaoglu, 2017).

A high level of visual reaction time is crucial for demonstrating skills effectively in various soccer positions (Marancı & Müniroğlu, 2001; Göral et al., 2012). The visual command training group's significantly greater improvement can be attributed to this scientific basis. Additionally, for the human body to form a conscious response, stimuli must be effectively perceived by the central nervous system, which then develops an appropriate response (Alpkaya & Mengütay, 2004; Ertavukçu et al., 2021). Studies in this field often emphasise that the central nervous system processes visual stimuli most effectively. The perception and interpretation of visual stimuli in the brain, as well as the formation of an appropriate response, can yield faster results than in other sensory areas. Therefore, visual input can directly affect reaction time (Aral, 2021);

Ercan & Aral, 2011; Erişti et al., 2013). The more pronounced development of the visual command training group compared to the other groups in our study can be attributed to this scientific basis.

Similar findings have been reported in previous literature. For instance, Marancı and Müniroğlu (2001) reported that the visual reaction times of goalkeepers, defenders, midfielders, and forwards were 470 ms, 530 ms, 430 ms, and 490 ms, respectively. Erbahçeci (2001) compared the reaction times of basketball players and non-players, finding that the former had shorter reaction times. Imamoğlu and Kılıçgil (2006) evaluated the vital capacities and reaction times of 54 male athletes aged 10–13, finding no significant differences between reaction times and variables such as position, height, and weight. However, a significant difference was detected in the age-based analysis.

Overall, the findings suggest that regular training programmes can improve the reaction times of soccer players, which contributes to the practical demonstration of sport-specific skills required in football. In conclusion, the visual, auditory, and tactile command training applied in this study had a positive and statistically significant effect on the visual reaction times of child soccer players.

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